

PROCESSING OF PARTICULATE REINFORCED SILICON NITRIDE CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we present results on the potential use of second phase particulate inclusions in a Si_3N_4 matrix. The goal of the inclusion is to improve high temperature creep resistance by impeding grain boundary sliding by pinning and providing nucleation sites for recrystallization of the grain boundary phase. Results will be presented on research conducted to date. This includes an analytical model for residual stresses and critical particle size. Based on this model, several candidate carbides and nitrides were selected as potential reinforcement phases. The chemical stability of these and the Si_3N_4 matrix was investigated by thermal treatment followed by phase characterization using X-Ray Diffraction. Based on these results, candidate composite systems were identified.

INTRODUCTION

High fracture toughness, strength, and creep resistance are all desirable in silicon nitride for use at high temperatures but difficult to achieve simultaneously. An increase in fracture toughness is achieved when the volume fraction of elongated $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grains increases; commonly referred to as self-reinforced silicon nitride (SRSN) [1]. The amount of $\beta\text{-Si}_3\text{N}_4$ grain growth is enhanced when a sintering aid is used [2]. These elongated β -grains increase fracture toughness through crack bridging and the weak glassy interface (the result of liquid phase sintering) contributes to the intergranular fracture mode [1,2]. This microstructure is coarse and has low strength. Improvements in fracture strength have been achieved through refined processing techniques which lead to finer microstructures and minimized defects throughout the body. Due to the different microstructural requirements for high toughness and high strength, in general, the highest toughness materials do not have the highest strength. Finally, it has been a processing challenge to increase the high temperature creep resistance of SRSN due to glassy phase at the grain boundaries. This residual glassy phase softens at elevated temperatures allowing grain boundary sliding and/or cavitation which leads to creep deformation and rupture. Attempts to minimize the effects of this amorphous phase have focused primarily upon minimization and/or recrystallization of the residual glass [2,3]. Raj has recently suggested that instead of minimization of sintering aids there should be an optimum volume fraction of sintering aid which will allow secondary recrystallization of the grain boundary glassy phase. He concludes that the volume fraction of the sintering aid should be 8-15% [4].

In an attempt to overcome the problems mentioned above, Niihara has proposed the use of "ceramic nanocomposites" [5]. These composites, with nano-sized particulate reinforcements, have exhibited increased hardness, strength, and creep resistance at elevated temperatures. This increase in mechanical properties has been attributed to the presence of intergranular crystalline phases and the location of particulates at the grain boundary interface. It has been suggested that the particulates located at the grain boundary impede grain boundary sliding and/or cavitation which leads to creep rupture [6].

Second phase particles can influence the mechanical properties in a variety of ways. First, introduction of the second phase will induce residual stresses during cooling [7]. These stresses, in turn, have two significant effects. They can lead to spontaneous microcracking if the size of the inclusion is greater than a critical size [8,9]. These microcracks reduce the strength of the materials. However, if microcracks are not formed during cooling, then the presence of residual stresses influence crack path, and also lead to microcracks ahead of crack tip under applied stress [10,11]. These two effects in turn lead to enhanced fracture toughness. Thus, based on these factors, the residual stresses should be large and the particle size should be small. There is a practical limit to the inclusion size that can be used. Finally, the effect of second phase particles on high temperature creep is to impede grain boundary sliding. It has been shown that even very small particles can increase the creep resistance [6], however, the effect of particle size on creep resistance has not been systematically studied and needs further investigation.

Another important consideration when selecting a particulate reinforcement for Si_3N_4 is chemical compatibility. In order to be able to recrystallize grain boundary residual glassy phases, the chemistry of these phases needs to be understood. It is necessary to know what types of reaction products (none being the most desirable) are developed between the matrix and particle, the matrix and glassy phase, and the particle and glassy phase. An important criterion for the selection of the reinforcement would be for the particulate to be inert with both the matrix and the sintering aid.

The focus of this paper is on research currently being conducted on the use of particle reinforcement to impede grain boundary sliding in Si_3N_4 while maintaining high strength and toughness. Six candidate reinforcements were investigated in order to select which reinforcements would be most suitable. The residual stress and the critical particle size for each candidate was calculated and the chemical stability of the particle with the matrix material was investigated using X-Ray diffraction techniques.

CRITICAL PARTICLE SIZE CALCULATION

The residual stress in the matrix surrounding each particle was calculated using Equation 1 below [7], see Figure 1 for geometry.

$$\sigma_r = \Delta\alpha\Delta T/\kappa \quad (1)$$

The critical particle radius for each particulate-matrix system was calculated using the following equation developed by Ito, et al. [9]. For particle size $R < R_{C(\min)}$, microcracks would not form during cooling from the processing temperature.

$$R_{C(\min)} = 1.8\kappa G_C(\Delta\alpha\Delta T)^{-2} \quad (2)$$

where $R_{C(\min)}$ is the critical particle size, $\kappa = [(1+\nu_m)/2E_m + (1-2\nu_p)/E_p]$, E is Young's modulus, ν is Poisson's ratio, the subscript 'm' refers to the matrix and 'p' refers to the particle, G_C is the critical energy release rate for fracture (The value assumed here is for a glass, 8 J/m^2). This value was selected because fracture occurs in the grain boundary glassy

phase.), $\Delta\alpha$ is the difference in the thermal expansion coefficient ($\alpha_m - \alpha_p$), and ΔT is the temperature change upon cooling. For all the systems chosen, $\alpha_p > \alpha_m$, hence the interface is under radial tension at ambient temperature. Using Equations (1) and (2), the residual stress and the critical particle size R_c , has been calculated. These values are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1: Schematic of Geometry for the Calculation of Residual Stress and Critical Inclusion Size, R_c

Table 1: Summary of Variable and Results for Critical Size Calculation

$\alpha_m = 2.75 \text{ E-}6$; $\Delta T (^{\circ}\text{C}) = -1675$; $\nu_m = 0.245$; $E_m (\text{GPa}) = 300$

Particle	B ₄ C	BN	SiC	TiB ₂	TiC	TiN
α_p	4.50E-6	7.20E-6	4.70E-6	5.20E-6	7.95E-6	9.35E-6
$\Delta\alpha$	-1.75E-6	-4.45E-6	-1.95E-6	-2.45E-6	-5.20E-6	-6.60E-6
ν_p	0.207	0.200	0.188	0.185	0.188	0.200
E_p (GPa)	369.655	59.241	386.120	529.200	450.800	250.880
σ_r (MPa)	800.83	610.81	884.28	1256.71	2517.92	2475.05
R_c (μm)	6.134	3.163	4.986	2.792	0.657	0.526

Note: All values of the properties taken from Ref. 12 except for E_p for B₄C which is from Ref. 13. BN values are average of values parallel to c-axis and perpendicular to c-axis. BN value of ν_p assumed. All modulus values are for 20°C. The value of E_m was taken from Ref. 14.

From Table 1, TiC and TiN will lead to very high residual stresses and spontaneous microcracking can be avoided if the particle size is submicron. The lowest residual stresses are obtained for BN, B₄C, SiC, and TiB₂ have intermediate values of residual stress. Table 1 is a good guideline for potential reinforcement phases. It is clear that if very high residual stresses are desired, then particle size will have to be small. Once the effect of particle size of

creep resistance has been established, this table can be used as a guide in selecting the reinforcement phase and particle size.

These particles were then considered for chemical stability with the matrix.

CHEMICAL COMPATIBILITY

The chemical stability of the particulate reinforcement within the Si_3N_4 matrix was determined using X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)* techniques.

Samples were formed by dry pressing a 50/50 volume percent mixture of the reinforcement and the matrix. Dry powders were mixed and no processing aids were used. The processing aids were eliminated in order to strictly test the reaction between the two components (i.e. Si_3N_4 matrix and the particulate reinforcement). The powders were dry blended in an agate mortar and pestle and pressed into half inch pellets. These pellets were then packed in Si_3N_4 loose powders in graphite crucibles. Reactions were carried out in a induction furnace at 1700°C for 1 hour under 1 atmosphere of N_2 . A control sample of pure Si_3N_4 was also heat treated to insure that there was no contamination.

After heat treatment each sample was ground and XRD analysis was performed on each sample. Each reacted sample was then compared to an XRD analysis of an unreacted 50/50 volume percent mixture of the two powders. The relative intensities of the unreacted were subtracted from the relative intensities of the reacted sample. Difference maps were prepared for each sample type with the aid of a computer software**. By examining these difference maps, and the relevant XRD spectra it is possible to determine which, if any, of the components degrades and/or reacts within the sample during the above mentioned heat treatment. By subtracting the two runs, it was immediately evident if a new phase had formed. Evolution of a new phase was evident in the difference map by a spectra of positive peaks corresponding to the evolved phase. Conversely, a phase consumed during the reaction showed a negative peak in the difference map. The XRD spectra from the reacted runs were matched to Powder Diffraction Files to identify product phases.

Approximately half of the samples showed some form of reaction during the heat treatment. Examples of the difference maps developed for a system with reaction products and a system without reaction products are shown in Figure 2 (a) & (b) respectively. In both cases the degradation of Si_3N_4 is evident by the decrease in relative intensities of the Si_3N_4 . Si_3N_4 degrades to form Si and N_2 at elevated temperatures. This degradation is suppressed by heat treating in an N_2 atmosphere. Since the pressure of N_2 used during these experiments was only 1 atmosphere some degradation of the silicon nitride is to be expected. The amount of degradation in most cases was not pronounced in the XRD spectra, in most cases no evidence of Si was detected. It is most likely that the majority of the evolved liquid Si (melting point of Si is 1410°C . [15]) left the sample due to the highly porous nature of the samples or was simply volatilized. The results of the chemical compatibility analysis are summarized in Table 2. Since the amount of phases was not quantified, in Table 2, we have listed only the phases.

Figure 2: (a) Difference map for the $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-TiB}_2$ system which has reaction products, SiO_2 and TiN are labeled, (b) Difference map for the $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4\text{-BN}$ system which had no reaction products.

Table 2: Phases Present in Chemical Compatibility Analysis for Heat Treatment at 1700°C for 1 hour in N₂

* Boron appears to be volatile, no B peaks evident in XRD spectra. The SiO₂ formation is most like due to the residual O in the TiB₂ powders, approximately 2%.

The Si₃N₄ patterns for both the unreacted and reacted powders correspond to α-Si₃N₄. This expected result is due to the fact that the starting powders were rich in α-Si₃N₄ and there was not a sintering aid present to aid in the formation of β-Si₃N₄.

In examining the reactions listed above it becomes obvious that certain systems will not meet the non-reactivity criterion. The TiB₂ (6) is clearly unacceptable as a reinforcing phase and so is the B₄C (3). Boron nitride, titanium nitride and silicon carbide are ideal in their stability as a reinforcing medium for Si₃N₄. The TiC is interesting in that it degrades to form two phases that are stable within the Si₃N₄ matrix (7). This, if it is desirable to have both TiN and SiC as the reinforcement, it would be possible to achieve this *in-situ* by addition of TiC to Si₃N₄.

SELECTION OF CANDIDATE SYSTEMS

By combining the residual stresses, critical particle size and chemical compatibility study three systems were selected for further study. The B₄C system while having the highest critical particle size was one of the most reactive with the Si₃N₄ matrix therefore it was eliminated. The TiB₂ system was the most reactive and therefore eliminated on that basis. The TiC system was eliminated from further investigation due to the multiple phase reinforcement that would result from its use as the reinforcement. The three systems selected for future research are the Si₃N₄-SiC, Si₃N₄-BN and Si₃N₄-TiN systems.

These three systems also provide a rather broad range of residual stresses and critical particle size as seen from Table 1.

CONCLUSIONS

Through residual stress analysis and chemical reactivity studies it is possible to develop a criterion for selection of the reinforcement phase in Si₃N₄. The candidate reinforcement phases used in this study were B₄C, BN, SiC, TiB₂, TiC and TiN.

Of these, B_4C , SiC and BN had low residual stresses and fairly large critical particle size while TiC and TiN had the smallest critical particle size and the highest residual stresses.

By XRD analysis of sintered 50/50 volume percent Si_3N_4 -reinforcement samples it is possible to predict reaction products utilizing a difference map. The samples that were most stable within the α - Si_3N_4 matrix were SiC, BN, and TiN. B_4C and TiB_2 were very reactive with the matrix and produced multiple reaction products. TiC reacted producing two stable by-products, SiC and TiN. This interesting candidate system could be utilized to produce Si_3N_4 with multiple reinforcement phases.

Finally, a selection of three candidate systems for future work was made. These being: Si_3N_4 -SiC, Si_3N_4 -BN, and Si_3N_4 -TiN.

* X-Ray Diffractometer: Philips PW1710 Based

** Computer Software: JADE

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